

BIBLIOGRAPHIC INFORMATION SYSTEM

Journal Full Title: Journal of Biomedical Research & Environmental Sciences

Journal NLM Abbreviation: J Biomed Res Environ Sci

Journal Website Link: <https://www.jelsciences.com>

Journal ISSN: 2766-2276

Category: Multidisciplinary

Subject Areas: Medicine Group, Biology Group, General, Environmental Sciences

Topics Summation: 128

Issue Regularity: Monthly

Review Process type: Double Blind

Time to Publication: 7-14 Days

Indexing catalog: [Visit here](#)

Publication fee catalog: [Visit here](#)

DOI: 10.37871 ([CrossRef](#))

Plagiarism detection software: iThenticate

Managing entity: USA

Language: English

Research work collecting capability: Worldwide

Organized by: [SciRes Literature LLC](#)

License: Open Access by Journal of Biomedical Research & Environmental Sciences is licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License. Based on a work at SciRes Literature LLC.

Manuscript should be submitted in Word Document (.doc or .docx) through

Online Submission

form or can be mailed to support@jelsciences.com

 Vision: Journal of Biomedical Research & Environmental Sciences main aim is to enhance the importance of science and technology to the scientific community and also to provide an equal opportunity to seek and share ideas to all our researchers and scientists without any barriers to develop their career and helping in their development of discovering the world.

OPINION

US Pandemic vs. Politics

Liviu Popa Simil*

Nuclear Engineer, Physicist, USA

ABSTRACT

USA is in disarray, embedded in a strange recession, where GDP is decreasing, while workforce is growing, at least after government calculations, with lots of omissions included. Visibly US is in decay due to internal factors mainly, accelerated by wrong political actions, with deep disrespect to common sense, that triggers the action of external factors. Inflation is not entirely due to inappropriate response to pandemic, but is rooted in economy's dysfunctions, and external politics based on provoking external wars for the business of the "very few" who owns both parties sake. COVID did not disappear, is here, thriving, and takes a hard toll on US citizens, but was covered by other issues that captures the minds of a poorly educated population, trapped in information bubble.

Nor democrat or republican leadership, explained clearly the role of masks in fighting pandemic, and masks become now an object of fashion and political statements, being inappropriately worn. Due to this lack of understanding of how aerosolized nano-matter in form of viruses and bacteria propagates, the risk of having new pandemics over the winter is high. Viruses as SAR-CoV-2 continue to mutate and spread, and competes with new health threats as monkey pox, where 40% of US population suffer from a combination of Diabetes, Alzheimer's, Stroke, Heart Disease, Cancer, Chronic Kidney Disease and Chronic Lung Disease, aggravated by opioids, alcoholism stimulated by new recession, that will increase poorness and its consequences. It is important that government and its agencies to correct their attitude toward the real threats and to place health and safety of population above politics.

Introduction

US decay, is based on low national IQ due to last 70 years of education business, the divisions of population after political lines, the distrust in media and government organizations, the abnormal economic development that reduced manufacturing, high military spending to finance international turmoil and destabilization, while keeping at a minimum inside investment in own population. New trend in climate challenge, bring hazards humans making them come closer to pathogens during droughts and floods that displace people as global warming stimulating their spread. "Some 223 of the diseases, or 78%, were found to have been aggravated in the 3,213 cases of climate hazards' health impacts, while nine diseases were exclusively diminished and 54 (19%) were aggravated in some cases and diminished in others. The largest single factor was warming temperatures, with cases documented in which they had aggravated 160 unique diseases, followed by precipitation (122 diseases), floods (121), drought (81), storms (71) and land cover changes (61). Most of the diseases were spread by viruses (76), followed by bacteria (69), animals (45), fungi (24) or single-cell protozoa bacteria (23)" [1].

Discussion

In order to better understand the future, one has to be able to connect the dots between main facts, and to realize how they inter-correlate. A mouse never sees a threat into an elephant, in spite from time to time it steps on it, but this information is not transmitted in mice's culture, and the same happens with humans and climate challenge. Climate change, is the main threat, but is addressed with a lot of hypocrisy and superficiality, in fact being too little too late. In the last climate and "inflation reduction" bill, the immoral politics, aimed in serving the rich, made

*Corresponding author(s)

Liviu Popa Simil, Nuclear Engineer, Physicist, USA

E-mail: lps@lavmlc.com

DOI: 10.37871/jbres1541

Submitted: 11 August 2022

Accepted: 20 August 2022

Published: 30 August 2022

Copyright: © 2022 Simil LP. Distributed under Creative Commons CC-BY 4.0

OPEN ACCESS

Keywords

- Pandemic
- COVID
- Inflation
- Recession

MEDICINE GROUP

PUBLIC HEALTH

VOLUME: 3 ISSUE: 8 - AUGUST, 2022

some advantages for the rich to buy electric cars, being a favor for the rich paid by the poor, who will pay high price of gasoline. With an under-educated and divided congress the main investments are made into military, about \$1trillion/year, with a total debt of 1.5-3 GDPs, instead in rising the IQ level of population, by investing in education and social support for education, therefore the US brain power is IQ_{avg} (about 68) x Population 330 ml = 22.4GIQu (Giga IQ units), while China has $100 \times 1.4bln = 140$ GIQu; India has $72 \times 1.35bln = 97.2$ GIQu, and simple application of RAND corporations doctrines to contain these countries to lead the multipolar world is wrong, accelerating the decay of US hegemony, and drawing down all vassal countries (NATO, AUKUS), associated in bellicose military block in opposition to BRICS countries associated into an economic development block. During the last 20 years, US arrogant international politics, make it look like a trouble maker, instigator at social unrest and provocateur of fratricide wars, in order to find reasons to sell more weapons and make the huge US budget investment bring some profit, making the threats around us (global warming, nuclear war) more acute.

As one may see in figure 1, COVID pandemic that appeared in January 2020 and had the first pick in March, put stock markets in deep dive of more than 30%, with high recovery

after an influx of money, that did not address the cause, but generated an artificial trade increase after march 27. But was not this package which starts the inflation.

Inflation started after Tax cuts, when stock markets warmed up artificially, showing how disconnected is “Wall Street” from “Main Street”, than COVID appeared, and was inappropriately responded, with more money, in immoral spending bills with lots of bureaucracy and constrains. During Trump’s pandemic mismanagement 1/2 Million Americans died, and masks from protective tools become a political statement accessory, more than 1/2 of poor educated US population seeped in alternate realities and conspiracy theories world, an informational disease that acts as a pandemic, destroying the core of adhesion of a nation, where, the “beauty of American democracy remained the fact that every 2 years population is electing leaders they do not trust, from a very scarce offer. The future may bring again the no good choice election Trump vs. Biden, where people has to choose between hypocrisy and demagoguery, or two old man both so unfit for office, as national leaders. During Biden reign, at the beginning COVID was in recession, but CDC political decisions to please Biden, with a 4th of July mask free, eliminated the masks too early, without vaccination immune pool to be created, and

Figure 1 Synthetic presentation of main parameter evolution (Markets, GDP, Inflation, Gas, Covid, Other threats).

pandemic exploded, 100 million American were infected, and another 1/2 million deaths and counting, but in spite all of these nobody is talking about COVID, in spite there are 500 deaths/day and COVID diversify by mutating above BA-5, and other viruses appeared.

In fact, COVID is a big nano-machine, of about 120 nm in diameter, holding several billions of genetic code instructions. When COVID shield is broken, by medication, the internal content breaks in about 30-50 smaller units with diameters from 20 to 50 nm, mimicking a cocktail of viruses, similar to cluster ammunition, that spread in the body as functional entities, take shelter, and when immune system fades, it acts, offering medicine a wide domain of study into new diseases. The behavior is similar to chicken pox followed by shingles after 50 years. The future of medical research is large opened in front of us, by COVID, that may be associated with a 3.5 level of bio-weapon. The future military-bio-lab research is prone to bring genetic selective bio-agents that if released will bring an order of magnitude in sophistication of the medical research and prevention.

For short term, as figure 1 shows, we are in front of the growth of new pandemics, with a divided and confused population, unable to reasonably protect itself as a society, and being prone to more causality, aggravated by the economics. The war NATO forced Russia to get into to protect its vital security assets [2], and prevent a full scale nuclear war, accelerated US hegemony decay, by making 2 Slavic nations to kill each other for the benefit of western world. The observation in figure 1, augmented by collateral information, shows that no matter if a president is democrat or republican he paid allegiance to the military industrial complex, represented by stake holders and being the 0.1% percentile of the country. For the sake of a gain for them only of 0.5 tn/year Biden risked the fortunes of the entire EU and USA population of more than 500 tn, exposing to a direct nuclear confrontation with Russia [3]. The attempt of stealing the Russian business with EU with Natural Gas is prone to failure, because the US methane gas made by fracking contains associated radioactive components from underground Uranium decay. This gas LNG, exported in UK, and further exported to Europe by pipes, turn out of being radioactive and chemically toxic, and it turns expensive.

There will be almost no profit for US agents, and more after fracking, underground water is compromised and soon we might have to import water to drink, at a higher price than gasoline. The recent trouble made by Mrs. Pelosi in Taiwan brought an order of magnitude in economic complexity, activating China animosity [4], that will have an economic impact, reducing even more the capability of the US to protect its population against the main threat brought by global warming that stimulates the aggressive pathogens and bring them in close contact with humans.

Conclusion

The capability of a nation to survive and prevail in the future Climate challenge depends on the national cohesion, level of trust in government and local leaders, population IQ and its capability to understand the threats characteristics and develop optimal protection means.

The developing of protective means and policies depends on global cooperation and fast transfer of resources, which may be achieved only during peace time. The recent US actions to destabilize the planetary peace as it to maintain its hegemony are ill advised, based on greed and arrogance, and in fact will limit the resources and capabilities of US to protect its own population health and welfare. Remember the spring of 2020 where masks were in short supply, due to COVID in china that triggered aberrant, despicable advices from CDC, to mitigate the facts.

The wrong allocation of money into big pharma, with great WDC lobby, was another fact that contributed to the actual inflation and future shortages of basic products, further disturbed by immoral war provocations and sanctions.

References

1. Brian Bushard. Over half of infectious diseases could be worsened by climate change. *Forbes*. 2022.
2. David A. Determining the military capabilities most needed to counter china and Russia a strategy-driven approach. The RAND Corporation. 2022.
3. Nathan C, Bryan F, Edward G, Paul D, Forrest E, Howard J, Brent W. Overextending and unbalancing Russia, assessing the impact of cost-imposing options. 2019.
4. Gompert, David C, Astrid Cevallos, Cristina L. War with china: Thinking through the unthinkable. RAND Corporation. 2016.